

AIR-ABRASIVE SYSTEMS AND ABRASIVE MATERIALS FOR THEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14842512>

Abstract. This article contains a description of the physical and mechanical properties of abrasive materials used for air-abrasive systems. Description of the main representatives and description of their properties.

Keywords: physics, dentistry, biophysics, biochemistry, air-flow.

Air-abrasive systems or Air-flow systems, translated from English as "air flow", are used to remove pigmentation and plaque from the surface of teeth, including in hard-to-reach places. The aerosol stream is formed from a mixture of abrasive powder, water and compressed air. Coming under pressure from the tip of the instrument, the flow of particles effectively and quickly removes soft dental deposits, smoker's plaque, traces of coffee, tea, wine from the surface of the tooth.

Is the technique effective? Doctors K.-D. Bastendorf and Schmid from Germany conducted a series of clinical studies with a selection of experimental and control groups, as a result of which they came to the conclusion that "with supportive periodontal therapy, air-abrasive polishing with glycine-based powder is more effective in removing subgingival plaque than hand instruments, in addition, this method is safe and does not require large time costs", also numerous studies and years of use in clinical practice prove the effectiveness of the technique.

In the list of known requirements for oral hygiene powders, the first place is given to the safety of their use, the second place is given to the particle size, and the third place is given to their geometric characteristics. The safety of the powders used is determined, to an overwhelming extent, by the properties of the materials used. The grain size and geometric parameters of the powders affect the dynamic characteristics of the jet created by the tool at the outlet of the nozzle.

Powders should not contain particles of one exact size, because for effective action, both large and small elements are needed (small ones are polished, large ones are ground), therefore, powders contain particles of different sizes and here the question immediately becomes relevant: do all particles perform their functions equally well? Our answer is no. Why?

1. small particles dissolve in water, not reaching the surface of the teeth.
2. large particles have a lower speed, since more energy must be expended to accelerate them.
3. particles of medium sizes are efficient. They accelerate to the required speed and thus have sufficient energy to bombard the teeth and clean them from surface plaque.

If you look at the publications, it follows from them that the most effective are two particle sizes - 25 and 65 microns. In this case, powders with a size of 25 microns. Basically,

they remove soft plaque and polish the surface of the teeth. Powders with a size of 65 microns remove dense plaque and, in some cases, with thin enamel, significantly damage the surface of the teeth.

As for the shape of the particles, laboratory data have shown that the ideal shape of particles for polishing the surface of the tooth is spherical and the greater the roughness on the particles, the greater the abrasive effect on the tissue of the tooth. Consequently, the manufacturers take the spherical shape of the particles as a standard, however, some types of powders have defects on the particles in the form of roughness to increase their abrasive properties.

Let's consider some of the main materials for the air-abrasive system:

EMS classic powder - low-abrasive, fine-grained powder based on sodium bicarbonate with an average particle size for Air-flow technology. It has different flavors. For removing supragingival deposits and pigmented plaque, including "smoker's plaque".

Air-flow perio powder - suitable for processing the subgingival part of the root in order to remove biofilm, sanitize periodontal pockets, clean the surface of implants, helps to reduce the depth of periodontal pockets.

Air-flow soft powder is a low-abrasive, finely dispersed powder based on glycine. It is intended for the treatment of teeth of patients with sensitive periodontium, as well as patients who need frequent and regular professional hygienic dental procedures. Average particle size is 65 microns

Clinpro prophypowder powder - unlike conventional powders based on soda and calcium compounds, Clinpro prophypowder powder is based on glycine, which has a lower abrasive effect on the enamel surface and exposed dentin. This allows you to remove plaque without losing dental tissue, so cleaning with this powder can be done more often than twice a year, which is contraindicated when cleaning with powders based on soda and calcium compounds.

Flow-cleans corundum powder is suitable for both removing hard dental deposits and for preparing carious cavities. Contains an active abrasive - aluminum oxide (30-45 microns).

Manufacturer - Tehnodent, Russia

Air-cleans powder prof - the main component is sodium bicarbonate with a particle size that allows cleaning with a gentle effect on hard tooth tissues. If the cleaning stream accidentally hits the gum, lidocaine hydrochloride (0.5%), which is part of the powder, ensures painlessness of soft tissues. The powder has a pleasant refreshing smell and taste. Manufacturer - "Vladmiva", Belgorod, Russia. It differs from other powders in its relatively low price.

Thus, when choosing a powder for professional hygiene using the "Air-flow" technology, it is necessary to take into account the physicochemical properties of the powders, as well as the indications and contraindications for their use.

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